

Relationship between emotional intelligence and burnout: An empirical investigation of teacher educators

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ABSTRACT

Intention of this investigation was to explore if a relationship exists or not between emotional intelligence and burnout by examine a sample of 200 teacher educators that were selected by a purposive stratified sampling method from among of all teacher educators in District Gaya, India. In this investigation, two instruments were used to collect data, such as Weisinger's Emotional Intelligence Test and Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI). This research was correlation type so to analyze the data, were used Pearson correlation co-efficient and Analysis of Regression. Investigations found that teacher educator were not significantly different in emotional intelligence on the basis of gender, locality and teaching experience. Gender and teaching experience has nothing to play on burnout but locality has a significant difference on burnout score of teacher educators. Emotional intelligence and burnout syndrome have a strong negative association ($r=-0.221$), according to research results. Emotional intelligence had a significant contribution on burnout of teacher educators.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Teaching is a public dealing profession which demands more empathy, love, affection and care for the students. However, due to the changing demand of society this profession also came under pressure of professional needs. Teacher is an emotional laborer who continuously to cope up with emotional intelligence. But due to some unavoidable circumstances they have to face different challenges.

Teachers are highly expected to demonstrate positive emotions in all the way no matter what is happening in their inner cognition. Teacher faces many challenges in his/her life personally, professionally, socially, psychologically and other mores. It is very common for him to feel loneliness, lack of motivation, burnout, emotional stress, and improper feeling. All these factors not only suffer their professional life but also personal life. Balanced and well expected behavior from a teacher exhaust more mental and physical energy of a teacher resulting they start to feel mental stress and burnout. People who are emotionally intelligent are capable of balancing emotional demands [1].

As the fathers of emotional intelligence, Salovey and Mayer [2] represented emotional intelligence as "the subset of social intelligence that involves the ability to monitor one's own and others' feelings and emotions, to discriminate among them and to use that information to guide one's thinking and actions". In 1995 publication of the book "Emotional Intelligence" by Goleman [3], took the credit of making this novice phenomenon popular in the world. Very quickly concept of emotional intelligence becomes the center

attraction of the academicians, researchers and stakeholders. Goleman [3] explained emotional intelligence as “the capacity for recognizing our own feelings and those of others, form motivating, ourselves, and for managing emotions well in ourselves and in our relationships”. But long before of Salovey and Mayer [2] and Goleman [3], in 384-322 BC, Aristotle quoted “anyone can become angry and it is easy but to be angry with right person, to the right purpose and in the right way it is not easy” [4]. By this quotation he was emphasizing the role of emotions and emotional intelligence in human life. Darwin [5] also mentioned the importance of emotional intelligence by saying that “it is not the strongest of the species who survive, or the most intelligent, but those who are most adaptive to change”.

Emotional intelligence is defined as “ability to monitor one’s own and other people’s emotions, to discriminate between different emotional and label them appropriately and to use emotional information to guide thinking and behavior” [6]. Emotional intelligence as “emotional intelligence reflects one’s ability to deal with daily environment challenges and helps to predict one’s success in life, including professional and personal pursuits” [7], [8].

Teachers could be motivated towards their profession by developing emotional skills. It also helps them to counter with job stress. Personality types and traits were significantly related with the dimension of emotional intelligence of EFL teachers [9], [10].

Maslach's first research on burnout was conducted in 1976. Burnout was first described by Maslach and Jackson [11] as a condition characterized by emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and personal achievement. They explored that burnout is resulted from “labeling exploratory factor-analyzed items collected to reflect the range of experiences associated with the phenomenon of burnout” [12]. She further stated that prevalent theme found in the previous studies on burnout and they defined burnout as “problematic relationship between the person and the work environment, which is often described in terms of imbalance or misfit”.

Maslach's three-factor model was the subject of this study. According to this burnout model, there are three major causes that contribute to burnout, they are: 1) Mental fatigue, which is defined as a sensation of being mentally overworked and exhausted; 2) Depersonalization, which is defined as the formation of pessimistic emotions and behaviors toward one's profession; and 3) Reduced personal accomplishment, which is defined as a diminished sense of satisfaction and achievement, as well as a tendency to adversely assess one's own job performance [11].

Several surveys have shown that emotional intelligence is important in people's lives. It also aids in his successful management of stress and job burden [13], [14]. Several researches on emotional intelligence and burnout in teachers are available. The majority of the research found a connection between teacher burnout and emotional intelligence [14]-[18].

Emotional intelligence and stress have been shown to have a negative association. Emotional intelligence was shown to be helpful in coping with emotional stress. School teachers' emotional maturity is deteriorating as a result of burnout [19]. Several researches looked into the connection between emotional activity and teacher burnout [20]-[22]. These studies found no statistically important connection between emotional intelligence and burnout.

Today, burnout considers as one of the most debatable issues among the researchers and stakeholders. It's also linked to and to blame for the negative consequences of emotional labour. Burnout happens as a result of the pressures that staff, professors, and other professions face. Stress or mental pressure, caused by any reasons or sources, creates burnout [13]. Burnout mostly appeared among the workers in social interaction mode because of increasing demand of social satisfaction in the jobs. If they do not have capabilities to make effective communication, they may fall victim of burnout [23]. Work overload, uncompetitive administration, low salaries, non-cooperation of family and employer, improper arrangements of classroom environment were found significant factors responsible for the burnout among teachers [24].

Emotional intelligence has a direct relationship with burnout, where emotional intelligence is high there is less chances to become prone of burnout. Social worker and professional who have low emotional intelligence were found more prey of burnout. They showed less resilience to stress [25]-[27]. In his research, Mende [28] discovered a connection between emotional intelligence and teacher burnout among 49 secondary school teachers. The three dimensions of burnout i.e., emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, personal accomplishment and emotional intelligence, were shown to have a significant correlation. This connection was also found in terms of gender and ethnicity [29].

In other studies, emotional intelligence and burnout were significantly correlated. On 64 secondary high school teachers, De Vito [22] found a significant relationship between personal accomplishment dimension of burnout and overall emotional intelligence. Positive relationship was there between burnout and both subscales of emotional intelligence i.e., interpersonal and intrapersonal. This study did not find any significant relationship among three dimensions of burnout i.e., emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and personal accomplishment.

On the basis of above scholarly researches, the current research could assist academic personals, academic administrators and other stakeholders to understand how emotions can impact the burnout and stress, which if persist, could result in the mitigation of burnout. This investigation of emotional intelligence as it relates to teacher educators' burnout may lead to new and better ways to help teacher educators.

2. METHOD AND PROCEDURE

2.1. Research design

In terms of the current investigation's analysis style, it was a descriptive study. Quantitative research is the process of developing and testing statistical models, assumptions, and observations about phenomena.

2.2. Research method

In this investigation, the survey method was used. The descriptive analysis approach was used in this study. If a researcher needs to gather data on phenomena that cannot be directly studied, surveys may be helpful.

2.3. Population

Magadh University (State University) and Central University of South Bihar (Central University) are the two universities in Gaya district, India. Magadh University is an affiliating university, whereas the Central University of South Bihar is not. Gaya district had many Magadh University-affiliated teacher training institutes. The study's population included all teacher educators in the Gaya district, India.

2.4. Sample

From the above-mentioned population, two hundred teacher educators were chosen as the study's sample, with fair representation of all group as stated in the objectives. The survey included 130 men and 70 women, 116 city dwellers and 84 rural dwellers. There were 156 participants with fewer than 5 years of experience and 44 with more than 5 years.

2.5. Instruments used

The following instruments were used in this study: 1) Weisinger's emotional intelligence test. The respondents' emotional intelligence was assessed using Weisinger's instrument, "Developing Emotional Intelligence." It's a well-respected and commonly used research tool; 2) Maslach burnout inventory (MBI). The MBI is available in three versions: the original MBI-HSS (Human Services Survey), the MBI-GS (General Survey), and the MBI-ES (Educators Survey). and the survey used in this study, the MBI-ES (Educators Survey). Emotional exhaustion has a reliability coefficient of 0.89 (frequency) and 0.86 (intensity), depersonalization has a reliability coefficient of 0.71 (frequency) 0.72 (intensity), and professional accomplishment has a reliability coefficient of 0.81 (frequency) 0.81 (intensity).

2.6. Statistical procedure used

Following the scoring, a statistical approach was used. The significance of the difference between the mean scores of emotional intelligence and burnout scores of teacher educators was determined using analysis of variance. On the scores obtained for the analysis, the investigator used the following mentioned statistical approaches or methods: Mean, S.D, Critical Ratio, ANOVA.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Analysis of distribution of emotional intelligence teacher educators of Gaya district

There were three criteria for the assessing the level of emotional intelligence which are mentioned Table 1. According to Table 1, the mean value and standard deviation of overall emotional intelligence ratings of Gaya district teacher educators are 35.69 and 9.69, respectively. Teacher educators with mean scores of 45 and above are classified as having high emotional intelligence, those with mean scores of 26 and lower are classified as having low emotional intelligence, and those with mean scores of 27 to 46 are classified as having moderate emotional intelligence. As a result, 11.5% (n=23) teacher educators considered as extreme emotionally intelligent, 73.5% (n=147) observed as moderate emotionally intelligent, and rest 15% (n=30) were observed as poor on emotional intelligent. It shows that the majority of teacher educators have a modest level of emotional intelligence, with low and strong emotional intelligence following closely behind.

Table 1. Distribution of levels of emotional intelligence among teacher educators

Mean	SD	Levels of emotional intelligence								
		High			Moderate			Low		
		Criteria	No	%	Criteria	No	%	Criteria	No	%
115.41	43.24	>159	35	17.5	73-158	126	63	<72	39	19.5

3.2. Analysis of distribution of levels of burnout among teacher educators

Table 2 shows the different level of burnout of the teacher educators. According to Table 2, the Burnout scores of Gaya district teacher educators are $M=61.93$ and $SD=16.99$. Teacher educators with mean scores of 79 and above are classified as high burnout, those with mean scores of 45 and lower are classified as medium burnout, and those with scores of 46 to 78 are classified as moderate burnout. As a result, 35 (17.5%), 148 (74%), and 17 (8.5%) teachers' educators were found to be suffering from extreme, mild, and low burnout, respectively. It shows that the majority of teacher educators suffer from mild burnout, followed by extreme and low burnout.

Table 2. Distribution of levels of burnout among teacher educators of Gaya district

Mean	SD	Levels of burnout								
		High			Moderate			Low		
		Criteria	No	%	Criteria	No	%	Criteria	No	%
61.93	16.99	>79	35	17.5	46-78	148	74	<45	17	8.5

3.3. Research question 1: To study the levels of emotional intelligence among teacher educators of Gaya district on the basis of their characteristics (sex, residential location and experience in teaching)

Detailed comparison of emotional intelligence of different sub groups are mentioned in Table 3. The obtained $p=.624$, which is higher ($p>.05$) than the .05 degree of importance, is seen in Table 3. It means that at the .05 level of significance, there is no significant difference in the Emotional intelligence mean scores of male ($M=116.42$, $SD=46.94$) and female ($M=113.51$, $SD=35.60$) Gaya district teacher educators, $t(198)=-.491$, $p=.624$. As a result, sex has no impact on the emotional intelligence of Gaya district teacher educators.

Table 3. Comparison of emotional intelligence mean scores of teacher educators

Gender	N	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value
Male	130	116.42	46.94	0.491	0.624
Female	70	113.51	35.60		
Rural	84	111.23	46.28	-1.164	0.256
Urban	116	118.43	40.84		
Less experienced	156	112.63	43.07	-1.718	0.087
More experienced	44	125.25	42.88		

The obtained $p=.256$ is higher ($p>.05$) than the .05 degree of significance as seen in Table 3. It means that at the .05 level of significance, there is no significant difference in the Emotional Intelligence mean scores of rural ($M=111.23$, $SD=46.28$) and urban ($M=118.43$, $SD=40.84$) Gaya district teacher educators, $t(198)=-1.164=.256$. As a result, the location has no effect on the emotional intelligence of teacher educators in the Gaya district.

The obtained $p=.087$, which is higher ($p>.05$) than the .05 degree of importance, is seen in Table 3. It means that at the .05 level of significance, $t(198)=-1.718=.087$, there is no significant difference in the Emotional intelligence mean scores of inexperienced ($M=112.63$, $SD=43.07$) and experienced ($M=125.25$, $SD=42.88$) teacher educators of Gaya district. As a result, teaching experience has no impact on the emotional intelligence of Gaya district teacher educators. Inter and Intra correlation of emotional intelligence of participants is mentioned in Table 4. Table 4 indicates the dimension wise correlation between the Intra and Inter i.e., dimension of Emotional Intelligence. The relationship between Inter and Intra are positively correlated ($r=.854$) and significant at $p<.01$. The $r=.854$ indicates magnitude of the correlation is high.

Table 4. Correlation within the dimension of emotional intelligence

Emotional intelligence		Inter	Intra
Inter	Pearson Correlation	1	.854*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	200	200
Intra	Pearson Correlation	.854*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	200	200

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

3.4. Research question 2: To study the levels of burnout among Gaya district teacher educators based on their characteristics, such as sex, residential location and experience in teaching

Comparison between the burnout of different groups is shown in Table 5. Table 5 shows that p value was 0.861, which is higher ($p > 0.05$) than the 0.05 degree of significance. It means that there is no significant difference in the Burnout mean scores of male ($M=62.08$, $SD=17.14$) and female ($M=61.64$, $SD=16.84$) teacher educators in the Gaya district at the .05 level of significance, $t(198)=0.175$, $p=0.861$. As a result, sex has no effect on teacher burnout in the Gaya district.

Table 5. Comparison of burnout mean scores of teacher educators

Gender	N	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value
Male	130	62.08	17.14	0.175	0.861
Female	70	61.64	16.84		
Rural	84	64.78	16.82	2.038	0.043
Urban	116	59.86	16.90		
Less experienced	156	61.94	18.72	0.028	0.977
More experienced	44	61.89	8.55		

Table 5 indicates that $p=0.043$ was obtained, which is less than the significance threshold of 0.05 ($p=0.05$). It means that there is a significant difference in the Burnout mean scores of rural ($M=64.78$, $SD=16.82$) and urban ($M=59.86$, $SD=16.90$) teacher educators in the Gaya district at the .05 level of significance ($t(198)=2.038$, $p=0.043$). The mean score favor Gaya's teacher educators in rural areas. Thus, rural teacher educators in the Gaya region were found to be more burned out than urban teacher educators.

Table 5 shows that the obtained $p=0.977$, which is greater than the .05 level of significance ($p > 0.05$). It means that at the 0.05 level of significance, there is no significant difference in the Burnout mean scores of less experienced ($M=61.94$, $SD=18.72$) and more experienced ($M=61.89$, $SD=8.55$) Gaya district's teacher educators, $t(198)=0.028$, $p=0.977$. Thus, teaching experience has no impact on the burnout of Gaya district teacher educators. Dimension wise burnout correlation is showing in Table 6.

Table 6 indicates the dimension wise correlation between the dimensions of Burnout. The relationship between Depersonalization and Burnout are positively correlated ($r=.363$) and significant at $p < .01$. The $r=.363$ indicates magnitude of the correlation is moderate. The relationship between Personal Accomplishment and burnout are positively correlated ($r=.127$) and significant at $p < .01$. The $r=.127$ indicates magnitude of the correlation is small. The relationship between Personal Achievement and Depersonalization are positively correlated ($r=.035$) and significant at $p < .01$. The $r=.035$ indicates magnitude of the correlation is small.

Table 6. Correlation within the dimension of burnout

	Burn out	Burnout	Depersonalization	Personal achievement
Burn out	Pearson correlation			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	--		
	N			
Depersonalization	Pearson correlation	.363**		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	--	
	N	200		
Personal accomplishment	Pearson correlation	.127	.035	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.074	.618	--
	N	200	200	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

3.5. Research question 3: To study the relationship between emotional intelligence and burnout of teacher educators of Gaya district

This study discovered a negative relationship between emotional intelligence and teacher educator’s burnout as seen in Table 7. According to Table 7, the association between emotional intelligence and burnout among Gaya district teacher educators is $r=-0.221$ and $p=.002$. At the .05 level of significance, there is a strong negative association between Emotional Intelligence and Burnout of Gaya District teacher educators, $r=-.221$, $N=200$, $p=.002$. The r value of -0.221 suggests a negative relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Burnout among Gaya district teacher educators. Substantial correlation may be observed in following scatter plot as shown in Figure 1.

Table 7. Correlation between emotional intelligence and burnt out of teacher educators

Variable	Emotional intelligence	Burnout
Emotional intelligence	Pearson correlation	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	-0.221*
	N	200
Burnout	Pearson correlation	-0.221*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	-0.002
	N	200

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Figure 1. Scatter plot showing a strong positive relationship between emotional intelligence and burnout

3.6. Research question 4: To study whether emotional intelligence contributes burnout among teacher educators of Gaya district

The Correlation Coefficient (r) is -0.221 as shown in Table 8, indicating that this correlation is negative. Emotional intelligence explains 4.9% of the difference in burnout, according to $R^2=0.049$. As a result, there is a negative relationship between emotional intelligence and burnout among Gaya district teacher educators. Table 9 depicts the relationship between teacher educators' emotional maturity and burnout.

Table 8. Model summary showing the correlation coefficient for emotional intelligence and burnout of teacher educators of Gaya district

Model	R	R square	Adjusted R square	Std. Error of the estimate
1	-0.221 ^a	0.049	0.044	16.61925

a. Predictors: (Constant), Emotional intelligence; b. Dependent variable: Burnout

Table 9. ANOVA summary showing significance of regression for teacher educators

Model	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Regression	2803.557	1	2803.557	10.150	0.002 ^a
Residual	54687.463	198	276.199		
Total	57491.020	199			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Emotional intelligence; b. Dependent variable: Burnout

The obtained p value is ($p=0.05$) less than the 0.05 degree of importance as seen in the ANOVA shown in Table 9. As a result, at the 0.05 stage of importance, the regression model is statistically important, $F(1, 198)=10.150$, $p=.000$. This suggests that emotional intelligence accounts for a significant proportion of the difference in Burnout mean ratings. Table 10 lists the regression equations and regression analysis.

Table 10. Coefficient of regression equation resulting from linear regression analysis for teacher educators

Model	Un-standardized coefficients		Standardized coefficients		t	Sig.	95% CI for B	
	B	Std. Error	Beta				Lower bound	Upper bound
(Constant)	51.913	3.357			15.466	0.000	45.293	58.532
Emotional intelligence	0.087	0.027	-0.221		3.186	0.002	0.033	0.141

a. Dependent variable: Total burnout

Both the intercept (constant) and slope (Emotional intelligence) are important at in the above linear regression coefficient table. 05 level of significance, $t=3.186$, $p=0.002$, $\beta=-0.221$, with a slope estimation of 0.087 and an intercept estimate of 51.913. That is, emotional intelligence firmly supports a reduction in Burnout mean scores, and emotional intelligence predicts Burnout (Y) among Gaya district teacher educators. Thus, regression equation for predicting Burnout from Emotional intelligence will be:

$$\text{Burnout}(Y) = 51.913 + 0.087 (\text{Emotional intelligence})$$

The findings show that the slope of the real regression line is somewhere between 0.033 and 0.141, with a 95% confidence interval. In histogram, P-P map, and scatter plot, residual check of linear regression analysis is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Normal P-P plot with regression standardized residuals from emotional intelligence and burnout variables from linear regression analysis

4. DISCUSSION

This study was conducted with a sample of 200 teacher educator of Gaya district of Bihar state, India. In overall sample 11.50% teacher educator were found high emotionally intelligent. 73.50% and 15.00% were found moderate and low on emotional intelligence respectively. In same way 17.50%, 74.00% and 8.50% were found high, moderate and low on the level of burnout.

A major variation in emotional intelligence was discovered between male and female teachers in this research. In comparison, male teachers were more emotionally intelligent. The findings of this study are consistent with those of other scholars [30]-[32]. This study found no significance difference in the scores of emotional intelligence of urban and rural teacher educators. This finding is also supported by earlier researches [33], [34]. There is a significant variation in emotional maturity based on the teaching experience's aspect. It is also been discovered that the level of emotional intelligence rises in parallel with the number of years of experience. This study's findings are consistent with those of another research [35], [36].

Male and female teacher educators were not significantly differ on burnout scores. Higher mean value of male teacher educators indicates that they were feeling more burnout. Results of the studies of Copper and Davidson [37] also support the finding of this study [38]-[40]. The burnout of teacher educators differs significantly depending on whether they live in an urban or rural environment. In contrast to their urban counterparts, rural teacher educators had higher mean scores, indicating that they were more burnt out. There was no significant difference in burnout scores for teacher educators with less and more experience. Capel [41] also revealed same relationship, but study of Friedman [42] was contradictory to this finding.

In this study emotional intelligence and burnout found negatively correlated. This relationship was significant at 0.05 level of significance. It is realized that the burnout levels decrease as the emotional intelligence levels of teacher educators increases. Finding of this research is consonant with the findings of the earlier researches [43]-[45]. It was also statistically revealed that emotional intelligence is significantly contributed in burnout of teacher educators. Results of this study were also supported by the study of Benson, Truskette and Findlay [46], [47].

Emotional intelligence, motivation, and mood swings have also been shown to predict burnout. Both aspects of emotional intelligence were linked to burnout causes. Burnout could be mitigated by the regular intervention and counseling programs of work professionals [20]. [48]. Result of this study was also in line with the study of Akomolafe and Papoola [49] who found emotional intelligence when taken as a whole significantly predicts burnout. They carried out their study of 300 teachers of secondary schools.

In another research it was stated that emotionally intelligent teachers are fewer victims to the stress and might easily cope up with the awkward or hostile situations. Teachers who know how to tackle with emotions may easily create an adaptive environment and gets success [8].

5. CONCLUSION

This study explored the importance of emotional intelligence for teacher educators on controlling and mitigation the effect of burnout in their professional life. Being a teacher is not an easy task because the teacher who is responsible for making and shaping the future of his or her students. The role of teacher is continuously going to be crucial. On one hand he or she has to perform his or her duty up to the mark and expectation of the employer and on other hand has to maintain balance in his or her both lives i.e., professional and personal. This fast changing and high demanding era need more monitoring and mentoring of the teacher's emotional health.

Both public and private authorities are highly recommended to diagnose the problems of teacher and their mitigation. More counselling and mentoring session should be organized for the teachers. Obviously if teachers are free of burnout and other psychological pressure, they can effectively convert their students in human capital which is the most precious asset for a country.

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